

Data Management Plan (DMP) for Socially Sustainable Circular Economy research project

Version 2

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines a comprehensive strategy for the collection, storage, analysis, and sharing of data in the study of social sustainability within circular economy (CE) practices. The plan ensures that the data generated throughout the study will be managed securely, ethically, and in alignment with the research objectives and goals.

The study seeks to investigate the social sustainability of CE governance at the local (municipal) level in Latvia, with a specific focus on applying the Fundamental Human Needs (FHN) theory. This theory emphasizes a human-centered approach to CE governance, which will be explored through a micro-level analysis. The research will examine individual perspectives on CE practices, as well as the factors that facilitate or hinder these practices.

FHN will be analyzed in relation to the CE governance instruments using the PESTEL framework, which considers Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legislative factors. The concept of access to resources—including information, skills, infrastructure, and decision-making processes—will be central to understanding CE practices within specific municipal contexts. In-depth case studies will be conducted in three municipalities to capture a nuanced view of local-level CE governance. These municipalities will be selected based on their diversity, depth of content, and interest in participating in the study.

The research is designed within a holistic framework, drawing on the System Approach Framework (SAF), which examines the interactions between economic, social, ecological, and governance components, as well as the involvement of stakeholders. CE governance

will be studied from both multi-level (macro, meso, and micro) and multi-stakeholder perspectives. The study will focus on five priority material flows as outlined in the EU Circular Economy Action Plan: 1) transport/mobility, 2) food, 3) plastics, 4) buildings, and 5) textiles.

Data will be collected through multiple methods, including: 1) comprehensive reviews of scientific and grey literature; 2) qualitative data gathered through interviews and group discussions; 3) quantitative data obtained via an original survey questionnaire; and 4) multicriteria analysis (MCA).

The final outputs of the research will include policy recommendations for improving CE governance at the local and national level.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and resilience Facility
project "Internal and external
consolidation of the University
of Latvia"
(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Erika Lagzdina (orcid:0009-0008-5542-6240)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan \(DMP\) for Socially Sustainable Circular Economy research project](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines a comprehensive strategy for the collection, storage, analysis, and sharing of data in the study of social sustainability within circular economy (CE) practices. The plan ensures that the data generated throughout the study will be managed securely, ethically, and in alignment with the research objectives and goals.

The study seeks to investigate the social sustainability of CE governance at the local (municipal) level in Latvia, with a specific focus on applying the Fundamental Human Needs (FHN) theory. This theory emphasizes a human-centered approach to CE governance, which will be explored through a micro-level analysis. The research will examine individual perspectives on CE practices, as well as the factors that facilitate or hinder these practices.

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The final outputs of the research will include policy recommendations for improving CE governance at the local and national level.

Researchers:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" \(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007\)](#)

Project: [ASSESSMENT OF PRE-REQUISITES FOR PROMOTING THE SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN LATVIA: HUMAN SCALE DEVELOPMENT \(HSD\) APPROACH](#)

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

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4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[Stakeholder discussions \(focus groups\)](#)

This data set will summarize data and other information related to implemented social survey methods based on group discussions. Group discussions will be implemented in different research contexts, at different stages of the research and involving different stakeholder groups.

The discussions will utilize the World Café group dynamics method, incorporating elements of moderated discussion. The sessions will be moderated by the researcher, who will initially introduce the participants to the focus group guidelines. During the discussions, participants will be asked to document their input on worksheets.

This dataset will provide valuable insights into the collective views of participants from various stakeholder groups, offering a more nuanced understanding of the factors that influence CE practices at the municipal level. The data collected will be essential for triangulating findings from the interviews and contributing to a comprehensive understanding of local governance of CE practices.

Each group will be specified as an event with its title, goals, list of participants, summary of discussed key topics. Audio recording and Transcript of group work will be used in specific situations. The respondents will be selected to ensure representation of the key governance stakeholder groups: State, Municipality, Business, and Mediators (such as representatives from the education sector, NGOs, etc.).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection is:

- 1) to receive feedback on interim findings from the multi-disciplinary experts and decision-makers

2) to present initial findings to the local stakeholders and discuss in depth factors affecting (supporting or hindering) circular economy practices from the human centered perspective view point

3) to validate results and jointly generate solutions and recommendations for better practices

Each group will be specified as an event with its title, goals, list of participants, summary of discussed key topics. Audio recording and Transcript of group work will be used in specific situations.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Event

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Data will be originally created through specific targeted events

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Social science scientists, circular economy researchers and practitioners, policy makers at local level, business

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

n.a.

→ Metadata: Event ID/Code, Event title, Event form (In-person, Online, Hybrid), Date, location, participant roles (e.g., community members, local businesses), discussion topics.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

no

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

none

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

Comment:

Data will be collected and summarized in 1 month after event and made public. Their better publicity will be even facilitated reporting in LinkedIn or other social platforms

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Open access

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

It is widely internationally used platform

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Office

no

no

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

none

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Excel, txt, pdf

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

none

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Most appropriate for the intended publicity and access

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

n.a.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-09-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-09-01

Restrictions of data storage

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data validation takes place during project.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Project covers costs

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data manager

Data collection

Processing, verification

Coding

Storing

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Institutional responsibility under open science principles

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

Passwords will be used to access to data storage temporary files, firewalls will protect whole PC, institutional could ONE DRIVE

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Social survey on circular economy

Description of this data set informs on how social survey (written structured) questionnaire will be used in the research to collect data from diverse audiences to assess their attitudes and behaviors , and satisfaction of needs (FHN) related to circular economy governance.

Two sources of data will fall under this category of data set according to form how data are obtained:

1) **electronical documents** (word or pdf) of filled in questionnaires,

2) **Internet Survey** (Survey Monkey Software Platform or other), data will be processed using AI.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Social survey (written structured) questionnaire will collect data from diverse audiences to assess their attitudes and behaviors , and satisfaction of needs (FHN) related to circular economy governance. Two sources of data will fall under this category of data set according to form how data are obtained. Data will be gathered using structured questionnaire (updates of questionnaire forms and bilingual versions will be developed to better design for research purposes and meet respondents cultural differences) form in two ways

1) electronical documents (word or pdf) of filled in questionnaires, the respondent wont be personalized (anonymous), these data will be summarized and processed

in Excel form. This approach will be used at the Test phase of the survey, analysing limited number of responses of selected audience (up to 50)

2) by submitted answers in an Internet Survey (Survey Monkey Software Platform or other), data will be processed using AI. Estimated number of responses is 200-300.

Survey questionnaires will be granted open access after completion of the project.

Aggregated data will be granted open access 2 years after completion of the project due to intentions to use them for scientific purposes.

A questionnaire will be structured into six content blocks, along with a respondent demographic block:

A. Awareness of Circular Economy

B. Plastic products/items

C. Textile products

D. Electrical and electronic good

E. Transport

F. Food

G. Demographic data (gender, age, education, place of residence, housing type, income)

In blocks B-F, respondents are asked to assess: 1) their habits, 2) their experience with CE implementation, and 3) their satisfaction with CE services available in their surroundings. The questions are primarily of a closed-ended type, with some blocks containing semi-closed-ended questions (i.e., "other" options requiring clarification). Response options are provided on a 5-point Likert scale. The scale's units are defined with extreme endpoints based on the content of the question:

"no importance - substantial importance," "strongly disagree - strongly agree,"
"never - often," and "dissatisfied - very satisfied."

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This is a specific original questionnaire on social sustainability aspects of the circular economy in the Latvian context, there are not known open access data in this respect.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For social scientists and specific field of circular economy researchers ;

National and local policy makers

Business sector

NGOs and communities

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

1) File naming Convention (FNC): files will be named to allow following: Survey type, language, version, completion date 2) For questionnaires cryptic codes, question numbers

Survey type (online, paper-based), date of survey, respondent demographics (gender, age, income level, education level, location, housing form).

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

no

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Restricted use while data will be used for scientific purposes, articles, afterwards access to data for collaborative partners and other scientists upon request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

2 years after project completion

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Open access

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Commonly used in the research project I took part in, easy manageable, possible to see versions

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Office

no

no

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

none

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

MS Office

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

none

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-09-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-09-30

RESTRICTIONS WITH DATA STORAGE TIME IN ZENODO

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Verification by the researcher (false data, incomplete data, duplications will be identified and avoided)e

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project financing, institutional budget, zenodo.org platform free services

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Erika Lagzdina (orcid: [0009-0008-5542-6240](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5542-6240))

Data collection, verification, consent forms, internal temporal storage, storage for open access, meta data management, files maintenance during whole process and

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

In-depth interviews

The purpose of the in-depth interviews is to gather additional information on circular economy (CE) practices in Latvian municipalities. A total of 30 in-depth interviews will be conducted across three municipalities (10 interviews per municipality) to explore the perspectives of various target groups on the factors that either facilitate or hinder the implementation of CE practices in each specific municipality.

The interview instrument will consist of a semi-structured questionnaire with both closed-ended (with predefined response options) and open-ended questions. The questions will be organized into thematic blocks corresponding to the elements of the PESTEL multifactor analysis framework: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors.

The interviews will be audio-recorded, transcribed using machine intelligence (MI), and the transcriptions will be annotated, coded, and conceptualized into categories for qualitative analysis. A summary of the interview findings will be prepared for each pilot municipality.

The respondents will be selected to ensure representation of the key governance stakeholder groups: State, Municipality, Business, and Mediators (such as representatives from the education sector, NGOs, etc.).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the in-depth interviews is to gather additional information on circular economy (CE) practices in Latvian municipalities. A total of 30 in-depth interviews will be conducted across three municipalities (10 interviews per municipality) to explore the perspectives of various target groups on the factors

that either facilitate or hinder the implementation of CE practices in each specific municipality.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- MP3

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no specific data available on issue

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Scientists of circular economy AND PUBLIC GVERNANCERESEARCH,
SUSTAINABILITY RESEARCHERS; POLICY MAKERS

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Open access

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Erika Lagzdina (orcid: [0009-0008-5542-6240](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5542-6240))

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3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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